

**EFFECT OF ORGANIC MATTER DURING THE DETERMINATION
OF SEVERAL ENDOCRINE DISRUPTOR COMPOUNDS USING
STIR-BAR SORPTIVE EXTRACTION AND IN-TUBE
DERIVATISATION-THERMAL DESORPTION-GAS
CHROMATOGRAPHY-MASS SPECTROMETRY IN
ENVIRONMENTAL WATER SAMPLES**

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**EFFECT OF ORGANIC MATTER DURING THE DETERMINATION OF SEVERAL
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SPECTROMETRY IN ENVIRONMENTAL WATER SAMPLES**

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Abstract

The analysis of organic pollutants in environmental water samples requires a pre-concentration step. Pre-concentration techniques such as stir-bar sorptive extraction (SBSE) have gained popularity since they minimise the use of toxic organic solvents and can be considered as green analytical techniques. Similarly to other pre-concentration techniques, one of the problems when SBSE is used is matrix effect, which often occurs during the analysis of environmental water samples such as estuarine or waste water samples. The present work studied the matrix effect during SBSE coupled to in-tube derivatisation-thermal desorption-gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (TD-GC-MS) for the determination of several endocrine disruptor compounds (EDCs), such as alkylphenols, bisphenol A, estrogens and sterols, in environmental water samples. Firstly, variables affecting both extraction and desorption were studied to perform analysis under optimal conditions. Variables such as the addition of methanol or an inert salt to the donor phase, the extraction temperature, the volume of the donor phase, the stirring rate and the extraction time were studied during the SBSE optimisation. In the case of the in-tube derivatisation and thermal desorption step, the volume of the derivatisation reagent (N,O-Bis(trimethylsilyl)triouloacetamide with 1% of trimethylchlorosilane, BSTFA + 1% TMCS) and the cryo-focusing temperature were fixed (2 μ L and -50 $^{\circ}$ C, respectively) according to a consensus between maximum signal and optimal operation conditions. Good apparent recovery values (78-124 %) were obtained for most of the analytes in Milli-Q water, except for 4-tert-octylphenol (4tOP), which showed apparent recovery values exceeding the 100 %. Precision (n=4) was in the 2-27 % and limits of detection (LODs) were in the low ng/L level for most of the analytes studied. Matrix effect was studied using two different approaches. On the one hand, Milli-Q water samples were spiked with humic acids and apparent recovery values were studied with and without correction with the corresponding deuterated analogue. On the other hand, estuarine water and waste water samples were spiked with known concentrations of target analytes and apparent recoveries were studied as explained above. In general, matrix effect could be corrected with the use of deuterated analogues, except for 4-tert-octylphenol (4tOP) and nonylphenols (NP) for which [2 H $_4$]-n-nonylphenol ([2 H $_4$]-NP) did not provide good corrections.

Keywords: endocrine disruptor compounds, environmental water samples, stir-bar sorptive extraction, optimisation, matrix effect.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the complex process of harmonizing laws, directives and actions within the European Union countries, the European Water Framework Directive (WFD, 2000/60) is probably the most important international legislation introduced for many years in the water management and protection field. This Directive considers water management from a wide perspective, looking for the prevention of any future deterioration of water bodies, as well as the protection and improvement of the state of marine ecosystems, in order to obtain “a good state” of water bodies [1]. According to the WFD, the good state of the aquatic bodies is obtained when the concentration of the priority substances in water, sediments and biota are below the established Environmental Quality Standards (EQSs), which have only been fixed for water. All the European Union member states should implement management plans in their river basins, which include monitoring programmes. However, the WFD does not specify the analytical methods that have to be used, so there is an urgent need to develop monitoring tools and analytical methodology able to provide improved chemical and biological data at a lower cost in order to respond to the challenges of the various tasks involved in each type of monitoring [2].

Most of the analytes in the WFD list are organic pollutants (hydrocarbons, organochlorine compounds, organic solvents, pesticides and chlorophenols), although four toxic metals (mercury, nickel, cadmium and lead) and one organometallic compound (tributyltin, TBT) have also been included. Some pharmaceuticals, hormones and endocrine disruptor compounds (EDCs) have also been included as emerging contaminants in the WFD list due to their presence in environmental waters, the threat they pose on drinking water sources and the concern about their possible estrogenic and other kind of effects [3]. EDCs, defined as “exogenous substances that alter function(s) of the endocrine system and consequently cause adverse health effects in an intact organism, or its progeny, or (sub)-populations” [4], can have synthetic and biological origin and include hormones, insecticides, phytoestrogens or industrial chemicals. EDCs are often detected in waste water treatment plants (WWTPs) effluents and their receiving environments since not all micropollutants are completely removed in such plants [5, 6]. In fact, effluents from several WWTPs have been reported to be estrogenic to fish [7].

The determination of contaminants at trace levels in water samples requires of both an extraction and a pre-concentration step. Traditionally, Liquid-Liquid Extraction (LLE) [8, 9], as well as Solid Phase Extraction (SPE), [8-10] has been employed to this aim. Recently, and due to the importance reached by miniaturisation in the analytical chemistry field, other techniques such as Solid Phase Micro Extraction

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3 (SPME) [11], Stir Bar Sorptive Extraction (SBSE) or Supported Liquid Membrane (SLM) extraction have
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5 attained great importance in the pre-concentration of analytes from water samples [12-18]. These
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7 techniques minimise the use of organic solvents (green chemistry) and analysis time, and improve the
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9 sensitivity of the global analytical method [8].

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11 SBSE could be described as a liquid-liquid microextraction due to the analytes in the aqueous phase pre-
12
13 concentrate in the polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) phase. The larger amount of PDMS present in SBSE
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15 compared to SPME (around 50-250 times higher) outcomes on higher recoveries and handling larger
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17 sample amounts [19]. The thermal stability of PDMS allows desorbing the analytes thermally in the hot
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19 injection port of a gas chromatograph or, alternatively, chemically into an organic solvent.

20
21
22 In the case of polar analytes, derivatisation reactions are used in order to improve extraction efficiency
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24 and/or chromatographic response. Different derivatisation strategies can be employed when SBSE is
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26 coupled to gas chromatography: in-situ, on-stir-bar or post-extraction [19]. The last strategy (post-
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28 extraction) can be performed with both thermal desorption (in-tube) and liquid desorption (in-extract).
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30 When in-tube desorption is applied, a small glass capillary tube containing the derivatisation reagent is
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32 placed with the stir-bar in the desorption chamber (see Figure 1). In the second case, the derivatisation
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34 reagent is added to the organic solvent after stir-bar desorption. In-tube derivatisation has been used for
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36 the determination of alkylphenols [20], 17 β -estradiol (E2) [21-23] and sterols [22].

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39 Extraction techniques such as SBSE suffer of matrix effect when applied to real samples such as
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41 environmental water samples. In such cases, isotopically labelled analogues are often used in order to
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43 minimise such effects [19]. In the present work different variables affecting extraction and desorption
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45 steps during SBSE coupled to in-tube derivatisation-thermal desorption-gas chromatography-mass
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47 spectrometry (in-tube-TD-GC-MS) were optimised for the determination of alkylphenols (octyl- and
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49 nonylphenols), bisphenol A (BPA), hormones and sterols in estuarine and waste water samples. The
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51 effect of organic matter was also studied using two different approaches. On the one hand, Milli-Q water
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53 samples were spiked with humic acids and apparent recovery values were studied with and without
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55 correction with the corresponding deuterated analogue. On the other hand, estuarine water and waste
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57 water samples were spiked with known concentrations of target analytes and apparent recoveries were
58
59 studied as explained above.
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2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Cleaning procedure

No detergent was used during the cleaning of glass in order to avoid possible interferences produced by the detergent residues. Therefore, the material was rinsed with abundant water and then sonicated under clean acetone during at least 30 minutes or maintained in a clean acetone bath overnight. Afterwards, the material was rinsed with Milli-Q (< 0.057 S/cm, Milli-Q model 185, Millipore, Bedford, MA, USA) water. Finally, the glass material was dried in an oven at 450 °C for at least 4 hours and stored.

2.2 Chemicals and reagents

n-Octylphenol (nOP), [²H₄]-4n-nonylphenol ([²H₄]-NP), bisphenol A (BPA), diethylstilbestrol (DES), cis-androsterone (ADT), equilin (EQ), [²H₄]-equilin ([²H₄]-EQ), 17 β -estradiol (E2), [²H₃]-17 β -estradiol ([²H₃]-E2), testosterone (TT), 19-norethisterone (NT), progesterone (PG), coprostan-3-ol (COP), cholesterol (CHL), [²H₆]-cholesterol ([²H₆]-CHL), stigmastanol (STOL) and equilenin (EQN) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany). Nonylphenol technical mixture (NPs, Pestanal®) was purchased from Fluka (Steinheim, Germany), [²H₆]-biphenol A ([²H₆]-BPA) and 4-tert-octylphenol (4tOP) from Supelco (Walton-on-Thames, UK) and estrone (E1), mestranol (MeEE2), 17 β -ethynylestradiol (EE2), estriol (E3) from Riedel-de Haën (Seelze, Germany). Stock solutions for each compound and deuterated analogues were dissolved individually in anhydrous methanol in order to prepare approximately 5000 mg/L solutions, except for EQ, [²H₄]-EQ, COP, STOL, CHL and [²H₆]-CHL, which were prepared in dichloromethane. Besides, MeEE2 was prepared in acetonitrile. EQN was obtained directly at 100 mg/L in acetonitrile. Chemical standards were stored at 4 °C in the dark, and stock solutions were stored at -20 °C.

100 mg/L dilutions were prepared in anhydrous methanol weekly. Dilutions at lower concentrations were prepared daily, according to the experimentation.

Dichloromethane (HPLC grade, 99.8 %) and anhydrous methanol (HPLC grade, 99.9 %) were obtained from Labscan (Dublin, Ireland) and acetonitrile (HPLC, 99.9 %) from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain). Sodium chloride was obtained from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany).

N,O-Bis(trimethylsilyl)tri-fluoroacetamide with 1 % of trimethylchlorosilane (BSTFA + 1 % TMCS, Sylon BFT, 99:1) was used as the derivatising reagent and was purchased from Supelco. Stir-bars (10 mm

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3 x 0.5 mm) were obtained from Gerstel (Mülheim an der Ruhr, Germany). Humic acids (technical grade)
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5 were obtained from Fluka.

6 7 8 **2.3 Sampling**

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10 Estuarine water samples were collected from the estuaries of Bilbao and Urdaibai (Bay of Biscay, Spain)
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12 in May 2010. Waste water samples were collected at the WWTP in Bakio (Bay of Biscay, Spain) in May
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14 2010.

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16 Samples were collected in pre-washed amber bottles and carried to the laboratory in cooled boxes.
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18 Samples were filtered through 0.45 µm cellulose filters (Whatman, Kent, UK) and kept in the fridge at 4
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20 °C before treatment, which was performed within 48 hours.

21 22 23 **2.4 Stir Bar Sorptive Extraction from water samples**

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25 The pre-concentration of the analytes from water samples was performed using 10 mm x 0.5 mm stir-
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27 bars. 20 g of NaCl were directly weighed into a 125 mL extraction vessel and diluted with 100 mL of
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29 Milli-Q or natural water in order to obtain a 20 % (w/v) solution. Then, a clean stir-bar was added and the
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31 solution was stirred until complete dissolution of the salt. Afterwards deuterated analogues were added
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33 and the sorption of the analytes was carried out at room temperature and 600 rpm overnight. Once the
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35 sorption step was over, the stir-bar was removed and rinsed with Milli-Q water in order to eliminate salt
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37 residues, and finally, dried with a clean tissue.

38 39 40 **2.5 In-tube derivatisation-TD-GC-MS**

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42 The derivatisation and thermal desorption were simultaneously performed using a thermal desorption unit
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44 (TDU) (Gerstel) connected to a CIS-4 injector (Gerstel). The TDU unit has a MPS2 autosampler (Gerstel)
45
46 able to handle 98 coated stir-bars.

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48 Stir-bars were placed into a TD tube together with a glass capillary tube filled with 2 µL of BSTFA which
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50 was placed inside an insert on top of the stir bar (see Figure 1).

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52 Desorption and simultaneous derivatisation of the target analytes was carried out as follows: 30 °C (0.50
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54 min), temperature increase at 150 °C/min to 300 °C (held for 10 min). During the desorption step,
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56 compounds were introduced in the splitless mode at 75 mL/min into a CIS-4 injector, that contained a
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58 deactivated liner filled with quartz wool, and kept at -50 °C using liquid nitrogen (Air Liquide, Madrid,
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Spain) for cryo-focusing. Once the desorption step was over the CIS-4 unit was programmed to increase at 12 °C/s to 300 °C, where it was held for 4 min.

The TDU was installed in an Agilent 6890 coupled to an Agilent 5975 electron impact ionization MS system (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA, USA) and with a HP-5MS (30 m x 0.25 mm, 0.25 µm, Agilent) capillary column. The following temperature program was used for the separation of the analytes: 50 °C (5 min), temperature increase at 10 °C/min to 220 °C and a second increase of 3.20 °C/min up to 300 °C, where it was finally held for 5 min. Helium (99.9995%, Carburros Metálicos, Barcelona, Spain) was used as carrier gas at a constant flow of 1.5 mL/min. The transfer line temperature was maintained at 310 °C and the ion source and quadrupole at 230 °C and 150 °C, respectively. Measurements were performed in the scan (50-525 m/z) and in the SIM (Selected Ion Monitoring) modes. The m/z values for each analyte are summarised in Table 1. The first ion was used as quantifier and the second one as qualifier.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Optimisation of variables affecting SBSE

SBSE has been previously used for the determination of alkylphenols [22, 23, 24], BPA [22, 23, 25], estrogens [21, 22, 23] and steroids [22, 23]. However, few of those works [22, 23] perform a simultaneous determination of such a large amount of analytes. Besides, extraction conditions can differ from work to work [21, 22, 24] and, thus, a thorough optimisation of some of the variables affecting SBSE should be performed. In this work NaCl and MeOH addition, sample volume, extraction temperature and time, and agitation speed were studied using spiked (100 ng/L) Milli-Q water samples. pH adjustment is usually studied when analytes have acidic/basic properties. However, target analytes occur in the non-ionic form at the pH of natural waters according to the pKa values (9.7-15.1). Besides, Quintana et al. [26] proved that pH was not significant during the determination of alkylphenols. Therefore, pH was not studied in the present work. In the case of the acceptor phase, 10 mm x 0.5 mm stir-bars were used due to their availability in our laboratory.

The effect of MeOH and NaCl addition during SBSE of target analytes was studied by means of a central composite design (CCD). The ranges used for this study were between 0 – 20 % for NaCl and MeOH. The design matrix was fitted to a non-linear equation using the Statgraphics program (STATGRAPHICS,

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3 Centurion XV). Correlation coefficients in the range of 0.85 were obtained. Most of the analytes showed
4 similar response surfaces (built using only significant parameters ($p < 0.05$)) to EE2, plotted in Figure 2.
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6 As it can be observed, in general terms, the addition of NaCl had a positive effect. Similar results were
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8 obtained by Almeida and Nogueira [27] for steroid sex hormones, although a negative effect was
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10 observed for E1. No significant effect of NaCl addition has been observed in the bibliography for TT, E3
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12 and NT [24, 28]. Consequently, NaCl was fitted at 20 % (w/v) for the rest of experiments. In the case of
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14 MeOH addition, a negative effect on the extraction efficiency for most of the analytes was observed.
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16 Thus, it could be concluded that the presence of MeOH increased water solubility, whereas it decreased
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18 $K_{\text{PDMS,w}}$ of the target analytes. Therefore, no MeOH was added in further experiments.

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21 In the case of sample volume, although higher sample volumes decrease extraction efficiency [29], an
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23 increase in the mass of the analyte may increase chromatographic response [30]. Average responses ($n=3$)
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25 obtained for 30 mL and 100 mL aliquots were compared by means of one factor analysis of variance
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27 (ANOVA) for a 95 % confidence interval. Similar to the bibliography, where little effect of sample
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29 volume has been observed for polar analytes [31], sample volume was not significant for most of the
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31 analytes except for alkylphenols, BPA and ADT, which showed increased signals for higher sample
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33 volumes. In order to maximise the response for the latter analytes and due to the availability and low cost
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35 of the samples studied (estuarine and waste water), 100 mL aliquots were used in further experiments.

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38 Extraction temperature is studied during SBSE since it has two opposite effects. While at elevated
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40 temperature the extraction equilibrium is reached faster [32-34], $K_{\text{PDMS,w}}$ partition coefficient and, thus,
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42 extraction efficiency, becomes lower [34]. The stirring rate is also evaluated because it can accelerate the
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44 extraction and, thus, increase responses at a fixed extraction time. This fact is explained by the decrease
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46 of the thickness of the boundary layer between the stir-bar and the solution [34]. However, high agitation
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48 speeds can suppose lack of homogeneity and bubble formation and these effects can affect to the
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50 response. In this sense, extraction temperature and agitation speed were studied at two different levels, 25
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52 and 40 °C and, 600 and 1000 rpm, respectively. Extraction temperature had no significant effect and
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54 lower agitation speeds yielded better extraction efficiency for all the target analytes, except for sterols,
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56 which showed no significant effect. Therefore, both variables were fitted at the lowest values studied,
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58 room temperature and 600 rpm.

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60 Finally, the extraction time was studied under optimised conditions. In order to obtain the extraction time
profile different extraction times (15, 30, 60, 90, 120, 180, 240, 300, 360 and 1140 min) were examined.

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3 The time profiles obtained for 4-tOP, E2 and MeEE2 are included in Figures 3a, 3b and 3c, respectively.
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5 The results showed that in most cases more than 20 hours were not enough to reach equilibrium.
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7 Overnight extraction was finally chosen.
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9 10 **3.2 In-tube derivatisation-TD-GC-MS optimisation**

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12 During in-tube derivatisation-TD-GC-MS, the volume of the derivatisation reagent (BSTFA + 1 %
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14 TMCS) and the cryo-focusing temperature were studied. Desorption temperature and time were fixed at
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16 high values (300 °C and 10 min, respectively) in order to guarantee complete desorption of the target
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18 analytes from the stir-bar. Actually, when stir-bars were submitted to a second desorption (after refilling
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20 of the capillary tube with BSTFA + 1 % TMCS), signals lower than 1 % were obtained for all the
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22 compounds in comparison with the first desorption and, thus, no further conditioning of the stir-bars was
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24 necessary.
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27 Different volumes of derivatisation reagent (0.5 µL - 20 µL) were tested. Higher derivatisation reagents
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29 provided higher chromatographic responses but when volumes higher than 2 µL were repeatedly
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31 introduced in the instrument, blockage of the CIS-4 unit and overpressures occurred. Thus, derivatisation
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33 reagent volume was fixed at 2 µL.
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36 Cryo-focusing temperature is one of the most usually studied variables during TD. Since TD of stir-bar is
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38 long (up to 10 minutes in most cases), a focusing of the analytes is necessary previous to the introduction
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40 of the analytes into the chromatographic column. Lower cryo-focusing temperatures yielded better
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42 results, but once again, cryo-focusing temperatures lower than -50 °C caused blockage of the CIS-4 unit
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44 and, thus, -50 °C was further used.

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46 All target analytes except TT, PG and NT were derivatised under proposed conditions. Besides, E1 can be
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48 artifactly produced from the oxidation of EE2 when the latter is derivatised with BSTFA+1 % TMCS in
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50 the absence of a solvent such as pyridine [35]. However, during in-tube derivatisation, the formation of
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52 E1 was less than 1 % and was considered negligible.
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54 **3.3 Figures of merit**

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56 Since PG, TT and NT are not derivatised in-tube, they have been excluded from the validation section. E3
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58 was excluded as well since the calibration results were incoherent.
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3 Calibration curves in the limit of detection (LOD)-500 ng/L range were built and squared correlation
4 coefficients in the range of 0.972-0.998 were obtained. LODs were estimated and defined as the average
5 response (n=3) of the blank samples plus three times the standard deviation and were in the 0.8-70 ng/L
6
7 range (see Table 2). These LODs are similar to those found in the bibliography (see Table 3) and it should
8
9 be highlighted that the present work performs a simultaneous determination of 15 analytes.
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13 Extraction efficiency, defined as the amount of analyte extracted to the PDMS phase, was calculated by
14 comparing the responses obtained after the desorption of stir-bars that had been in contact with Milli-Q
15 water spiked at 500 ng/L and the responses obtained after the direct introduction of 50 ng of the target
16
17 analytes. For the direct introduction of target analytes in the CIS-4 unit, 50 ng of target analytes in MeOH
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19 were evaporated in an insert under a gentle stream of nitrogen. A 2 μ L capillary tube filled with
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21 BSTFA+1 % TMCS was placed on top of the insert and submitted to TD. Experimental extraction
22
23 efficiency values are included in Table 2 and compared to theoretical extraction efficiency values,
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25 calculated using the KowWIN software program (Syracuse Research Corp., Syracuse, New York, USA)
26
27 which is based upon a log $K_{o,w}$ calculator. Good correlation was obtained between the theoretical and
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29 experimental values for some of the analytes studied, except for the 4-nOP, E1, E2, MeEE2, STOL and
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31 CHL.
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35 Apparent recovery, defined as the recovery obtained after correction with the corresponding deuterated
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37 analogue, was calculated using Milli-Q water samples spiked at 100 ng/L. Good recovery values (see
38
39 Table 2) were obtained in most of the cases (62-124 %), except for 4-tOP, which showed values that
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41 significantly exceeded 100 %.
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44 Finally, repeatability (n=4) was studied using four Milli-Q water samples spiked at 100 ng/L and values
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46 in the 2-27 % range were obtained, similarly to the literature (see Table 3).
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49 **3.4 Effect of organic matter**

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51 Like in many other sample preparation techniques for trace analysis, the efficiency of SBSE can be
52
53 strongly affected by the complexity of the matrix involved [19, 36-37]. In environmental water samples
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55 substantial levels of dissolved organic matter may interfere with the extraction of the target compounds to
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57 the PDMS phase and, therefore, the extraction yield may drastically change from sample to sample.
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59 One way to minimise matrix effect is based on the use of deuterated analogues from the very beginning of
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the analytical procedure, as it has been done in this work. If the extraction efficiency decreases similarly

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3 for both the analyte and the deuterated analogue signal, deuterated analogues may compensate for the
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5 matrix effect.

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8 In a first approach, different amounts of humic acids were added to spike Milli-Q water and
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10 chromatographic peak areas were normalised to 100 % with and without correction with the
11
12 corresponding deuterated analogue. The behaviour of the analytes could be divided into three groups.

13
14 In a few cases (E2, EE2 and E3), no significant influence of humic acid addition was observed (see
15
16 Figure 4 for E2). Moreover, there was not a significant difference when correction with the corresponding
17
18 deuterated analogue was performed.

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20 In the case of 4-nOP, BPA, DES, ADT, E1, EQ, MeEE2, COP, CHL and STOL a significant decrease
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22 was observed in the presence of humic acids but this decrease was fairly well corrected with the
23
24 corresponding deuterated analogue (see Figure 4) for COP).

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26
27 In the case of 4-tOP and NPs a decrease of extraction efficiency was observed in the presence of humic
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29 acids (see Figure 5) but it could not be corrected with the use of [$^2\text{H}_4$]-NP. As it can be observed in Figure
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31 5, [$^2\text{H}_4$]-NP extraction efficiency suffers a higher decrease than the studied 4-tOP and NPs and, thus,
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33 apparent recoveries for 4-tOP and NPs exceeded 100 %.

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35 In order to guarantee that this lack of correction was due to a different behaviour of NPs and 4-tOP with
36
37 respect to the deuterated analogue and not due to an interference introduced by the present of organic
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39 matter, blanks of humic acid water solutions were performed. However, as no presence of target
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41 alkylphenols was observed, we concluded that the lack of correction was due to a different behaviour and
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43 not to the presence of interferences.

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45 In a second approach, estuarine and waste water samples were spiked at known concentrations and
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47 recoveries were calculated, with and without correction with the corresponding deuterated analogue (see
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49 Figure 6). In general, the results obtained are similar as those obtained during the humic acids simulation
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51 experiments. [$^2\text{H}_4$]-NP does not work as a good analogue for 4-tOP and NPs since recoveries exceed 100
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53 % . Sterolic compounds show a significant influence of organic matter but it is corrected using [$^2\text{H}_6$]-CHL.
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55 Recoveries for E2, EE2 and E3 are not affected by the present of organic matter and, for the rest of
56
57 compounds, better results are obtained after correction as a general rule.
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59
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4. CONCLUSIONS

A method has been developed to determine a variety of EDCs in environmental water samples based on techniques that minimise solvent consumption both during the extraction and derivatisation steps. Several variables affecting the analytical procedure, such as NaCl and MeOH addition, sample volume, extraction temperature and time, agitation speed, derivatisation reagent volume and cryo-focusing temperature have been studied and successfully optimised. It should be underlined that compounds such as TT, NT and PG were not in-tube derivatised, and that, the determination of E3 was not possible since it gave no coherent calibration curves. Finally, the effect of organic matter on extraction efficiency is corrected for most of the analytes studied, except for 4tOP and NPs, where the correction using [$^2\text{H}_4$]-NP is not properly working due to the different behaviour of the target analytes and the deuterated analogue. Another alternative analogue should be chosen, branched, in order to compensate matrix effects of 4tOP and NPs.

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1. Scheme of the desorption tube that contains the stir-bar together with a capillary filled with 2 μL of BSTFA.

Figure 2. Response surface of EE2 for the optimisation of MeOH (%) and NaCl (%) additions.

Figure 3. Time profile for 4-tOP (a), E2 (b) and MeEE2 (c).

Figure 4. Influence of humic acids on non-corrected and corrected recovery for E2 and COP.

Figure 5. Influence of humic acids on non-corrected (primary axis) and corrected recoveries for 4-tOP (secondary axis). Comparison with the behaviour of [$^2\text{H}_4$]-NP (primary axis).

Figure 6. Corrected and non-corrected extraction recovery values for spiked estuarine and waste water samples.

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107x135mm (96 x 96 DPI)

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121x86mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Review

153x101mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Review

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130x84mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Review

147x100mm (96 x 96 DPI)

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139x78mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Peer Review

168x106mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Review

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183x92mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Peer Review

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Table 1: m/z values of fragment ions of target analytes. First ion was used as quantifier and second ion as qualifier.

Analyte	4tOP	NPs	nOP	[²H₄]-NP	[²H₆]-BPA	BPA	DES	ADT	E1	EQ	[²H₄]-EQ	[²H₃]-E2
m/z	207/208	193/221	179/278	183	368	357/358	412/383	272/347	342/257	340/216	344	419/286
Analyte	E2	TT	EQN	MeEE2	NT	EE2	PG	E3	COP	[²H₆]-CHL	CHL	STOL
m/z	416/285	^a	338/295	367/382	355/356 ^a	425/359	^a	504/345	370/355	464/374	329/368	473/488

^a Not derivatised under in-tube derivatisation.

Peer Review

Table 2: Figures of merit of SBSE in-tube-derivatisation-TD-GC-MS.

Analyte	Log $K_{o/w}$	Theoretical efficiency (%)	Experimental efficiency ^a (%)	Apparent recovery ^b (%)	RSD (%)	LOD (ng/L)
tOP	5.28	97.9	79	147	26	0.8
NP	6.19	99.7	103	124	10	33
OP	4.12	76.0	46	99	12	4.5
BPA	3.43	39.2	20	105	5	8.7
DES	5.07	96.6	80	110	9	0.8
ADT	3.75	57.4	53	97	12	1.2
E1	3.69	54.0	5	62	20	5.6
EQ	3.52	44.3	50	100	2	7.4
EQN	3.76	58.0	- ^c	78	27	70
E2	4.13	76.4	28	108	15	7.0
MeEE2	5.18	97.3	7	83	14	28
EE2	4.52	88.8	55	101	19	40
COP	10.22	100	99	98	8	11
STOL	10.2	100	56	103	23	31
CHL	9.85	100	32	103	15	56

^a Amount extracted to the PDMS phase.^b Recovery after correction with the corresponding deuterated analogue.^c not determined.

Table 3: LODs and RSD values found in the bibliography for target compounds in different environmental water samples

	Sample	Method	LOD (ng/L)	RSD (%)	Reference
4-tOP	River water	TD-GC-MS	2	7.7-11.3	[20]
	Seawater	SPE-HPLC-ESI-MS/MS	0.14	20-30	[38]
	Waste water	SPE-derivatisation-GC-MS	13.0	5.4	[39]
	Waste water	SPE-GC-MS-MS	20.0	6.4	[39]
	Tap and river water	TD-GC-MS	2	3.8-5.3	[40]
	River water	SBSE-TD-GC-MS	1.2	3.8	[41]
	Estuarine and waste water	In-tube derivatisation TD-GC-MS	0.8	26	This study
	n-NP	River water	TD-GC-MS	0.5	3.9-5.7
Seawater		SPE-HPLC-ESI-MS/MS	0.12	20-30	[38]
Waste water and snow		SPE-LVI-GC-MS	18.5	11	[42]
		MEPS-LVI-GC-MS	96.4	4	
Waste water		SPE-LC/MS/MS	1.3	< 14	[43]
Tap and river water		TD-GC-MS	20	3.6-6.6	[40]
River water		SBSE-TD-GC-MS	3.2	6.1	[41]
Estuarine and waste water		In-tube derivatisation TD-GC-MS	33	10	This study
OP	Waste water	SPE-LC/MS/MS	1.8	< 14	[43]
	River water	SBSE-TD-GC-MS	0.1	8.3	[41]
	Estuarine and waste water	In-tube derivatisation TD-GC-MS	4.5	12	This study
BPA	River water	SBSE-TD-GC-MS	1	3.8-4.7	[25]
	Seawater	SPE-HPLC-ESI-MS/MS	0.04	20-30	[38]

		SPE-LVI-GC-MS	32.3	2	
	Waste water and snow				[42]
		MEPS-LVI-GC-MS	176.5	19	
	Waste water	SPE-LC/MS/MS	1.9	< 14	[43]
	Waste water	SPE-derivatisation-GC-MS	26.5	8.0	[39]
	Waste water	SPE-GC-MS-MS	2.5	1.6	[39]
	River water	SBSE-TD-GC-MS	0.6	4.1	[41]
	Waste water	SPME-GC-MS	300	10	[46]
	Estuarine and waste water	In-tube derivatisation TD-GC-MS	8.7	5	This study
E1	River water	SBSE-TD-GC-MS	0.2	2.6-3.6	[44]
	Seawater	SPE-HPLC-ESI-MS/MS	0.02	20-30	[38]
	Waste water	SPE-LC/MS/MS	1.3	< 14	[43]
	Waste water	SPE-derivatisation-GC-MS	8.5	6.6	[39]
	Waste water	SPE-GC-MS-MS	7.5	9.5	[39]
	Waste water	SPE-LC-LC-APPI-MS-MS	3.2	9	[45]
	Estuarine and waste water	In-tube derivatisation TD-GC-MS	5.6	20	This study
E2	River water	SBSE-TD-GC-MS	0.5	2.8-4.5	[44]
	Seawater	SPE-HPLC-ESI-MS/MS	0.3	20-30	[38]
	Waste water	SPE-LC/MS/MS	1.2	< 14	[43]
	Waste water	SPE-derivatisation-GC-MS	17.0	7.6	[39]
	Waste water	SPE-GC-MS-MS	27.5	10.2	[39]
	Waste water	SPE-LC-LC-	0.9	3	[45]

		APPI-MS-MS			
	Estuarine and waste water	In-tube derivatisation TD-GC-MS	7.0	15	This study
	Waste water and snow	SPE-LVI-GC-MS	6	13	[42]
MeEE2	Waste water and snow	MEPS-LVI-GC-MS	48.5	6	
	Estuarine and waste water	In-tube derivatisation TD-GC-MS	28	14	This study
EE2	River water	SBSE-TD-GC-MS	1	1.3-9.3	[44]
	Seawater	SPE-HPLC-ESI-MS/MS	0.45	20-30	[38]
	Waste water and snow	SPE-LVI-GC-MS	9.3	9	[42]
	Waste water and snow	MEPS-LVI-GC-MS	124.6	4	
	Waste water	SPE-LC/MS/MS	0.9	< 14	[43]
	Waste water	SPE-derivatisation-GC-MS	4.0	5.4	[39]
	Waste water	SPE-GC-MS-MS	17.5	8.5	[39]
	Waste water	SPE-LC-LC-APPI-MS-MS	2.7	5	[45]
	Waste water	SPME-GC-MS	20	9	[46]
	Waste water	SPE-GC-MS	10		
	Estuarine and waste water	In-tube derivatisation TD-GC-MS	40	19	This study
E3	Seawater	SPE-HPLC-ESI-MS/MS	1	20-30	[38]
	Waste water	SPE-LC/MS/MS	1.3	< 14	[43]
	Waste water	SPE-LC-LC-APPI-MS-MS	25	5	[45]